

Shamblin III Carotid Glomus, Complete Resection Without Vascular Graft Interposition: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Carotid paragangliomas are rare, highly vascularized, and slow-growing neuroendocrine tumors. Their Shamblin classification is based on their relationship with the carotid vessels, with class III being the most surgically complex due to intimate adherence to or invasion of the carotid bifurcation.

We describe the case of a 55-year-old female patient diagnosed with carotid paraganglioma, also known as "glomus carotid," encapsulating the internal and external carotid arteries, corresponding to Shamblin classification III. Complete resection without vascular graft interposition was performed. Hemostasis was achieved through direct suture repair. Postoperative outcome was satisfactory, with no neurological or vascular complications or recurrence at 6 months. This demonstrates that resection without vascular graft interposition is feasible in selected cases, with adequate dissection and primary repair, avoiding major complications.

KEYWORDS: Carotid paraganglioma, Shamblin III, resection without graft, vascular surgery, cervical tumor.

ABBREVIATIONS: Computed tomography (CT), intensive care unit (ICU)

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INTRODUCTION

Carotid body paraganglioma, also known as carotid glomus, is a benign, highly vascularized neoplasm originating from the paraganglionic cells of the carotid body. It represents less than 0.5% of head and neck tumors (1, 2, 3).

Clinically, it manifests as a slow-growing neck mass (4).

The Shamblin classification, first proposed in 1971 by Shamblin et al., is a surgical tool used to estimate the complexity of carotid body tumor resection, anticipate the need for vascular reconstruction, and make preoperative decisions, such as embolization, based on the tumor's anatomical relationship with the carotid vessels, especially the bifurcation (5, 6).

This classification divides tumors into three groups based on the degree of adherence or invasion to the common carotid artery, the internal carotid artery, and the external carotid artery (5, 6).

Shamblin I tumors are small, mobile, well-circumscribed, with little vascular adhesion or displacement. They do not completely envelop the carotid arteries, and surgical resection is straightforward, with a low risk of neurovascular complications (6, 7, 8).

Shamblin II tumors are moderately sized, partially adherent to or surrounding vessels, partially surrounding arteries without complete invasion. They require meticulous

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dissection to separate them from vessels and nerve structures (6, 7, 8).

However, Shamblin III tumors are large, tightly adherent to vessels, and voluminous, completely enveloping the carotid bifurcation, with strong adhesion or even invasion of the vascular walls (6, 7, 8) (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Shamblin classification for carotid body tumors. Common carotid artery (red arrow), Internal carotid artery (green arrow), External carotid artery (yellow arrow), Carotid body tumor (blue star). By Encinas-García Jorge A.

Resection usually requires complex vascular repair and, in some cases, the interposition of venous or prosthetic grafts. It is associated with prolonged operative times and the need for intensive postoperative care. They present a higher risk of nerve injury, massive bleeding, and postoperative complications (9, 10, 11).

Therefore, type III represents the greatest technical challenge due to its relationship with the carotid bifurcation, with a high risk of complications. However, in selected cases, vessel-preserving resection and primary repair can be achieved (12, 13, 14, 15).

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 55-year-old female patient from Torreón, Coahuila, with a personal history of primary hyperthyroidism controlled with methimazole. She reported good hygiene habits, regular aerobic physical activity, and no history of smoking, alcohol use, or drug addiction. She denied any family or surgical history.

The current condition began with the detection of a progressively growing left anterior cervical mass over the past 8 months, with exacerbation of symptoms over the past 3 months, including dyspnea, dysphagia with solids and liquids, and tenderness. Physical examination revealed a 4 x 4 cm, indurated, painful, and slightly mobile mass in the carotid triangle, displacing structures in the muscular triangle. Initial laboratory studies showed leukocytes $6.1 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, hemoglobin 13.3 g/dL, hematocrit 38.8%, and platelets $186 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$. Glucose 91 g/dL, serum creatinine 0.5 mg/dL. All other parameters were normal.

Head and neck computed tomography with intravenous contrast revealed a well-circumscribed, hypervascular mass with lobulated contours located in the left carotid bifurcation, measuring 4 x 4 x 5 cm. The lesion completely displaces and surrounds the internal and external carotid arteries, with partial loss of fatty separation planes and mild to moderate luminal stenosis without thrombosis. The common carotid artery is compressed in its distal portion. The mass shows intense and homogeneous contrast uptake in the arterial phase, with multiple visible afferent and efferent vessels, consistent with a Shamblin III carotid paraganglioma (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. Contrast-enhanced CT scan of the head and neck in the sagittal (A), coronal (B), and axial (C) planes.

The 4x4 cm tumor in the area of the left carotid body, indicated by the red arrow, is evident.

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Under general anesthesia and in the supine position with slight cervical extension and contralateral rotation, a left anterior cervical incision was made along the anterior border of the sternocleidomastoid muscle. Careful dissection was performed in layers until the carotid triangle was exposed. A tumor mass measuring approximately 4 x 3 x 4 cm was identified at the carotid bifurcation, with multiple feeding vessels, of mixed consistency (stony and soft zones) and circumferential involvement of the internal and external carotid arteries. Meticulous dissection of the tumor was performed, identifying and preserving adjacent structures, including the hypoglossal nerve, vagus nerve, and accessory nerve. The resection was performed en bloc, carefully separating the tumor from the common carotid artery and circumferentially dissecting the internal and external carotid arteries. During the resection, significant arterial bleeding occurred, which was controlled by direct repair of the vascular adventitia using 6-0 nonabsorbable sutures (Figures 3 and 4).

The use of a vascular graft or interposition of a prosthetic or venous segment was not necessary, resulting in successful direct repair of the affected arteries (Figure 5).

The patient was transferred to the ICU, intubated and sedated, for close postoperative monitoring.

FIGURE 3. Intraoperative image shows the left anterior cervical region, carotid triangle. A 4x4 cm tumor is delimited and highlighted in yellow.

FIGURE 4. Intraoperative image of the left anterior cervical region of the carotid triangle, following tumor resection. The common carotid artery (yellow), internal carotid artery (blue), and external carotid artery (green) are observed.

FIGURE 5. Surgical piece.

In the immediate postoperative period in the ICU, during extubation, the patient presented a massive cervical hematoma. A 300 ml surgical drain of the prefascial collection was performed, with no active bleeding identified. A Penrose drain was placed and the patient was closed in layers.

The patient's progress was favorable, with progressive withdrawal of sedation and extubation without adverse events. Stable vital signs were documented, the surgical wound showed no signs of infection or further bleeding, and the drain was removed. The patient was transferred to the ward, started on oral intake, and showed complete neurological recovery with no dysphagia, dysphonia, or cranial nerve deficits. He was discharged 7 days postoperatively without complications.

The histopathological study reported a solid, encapsulated, ovoid tumor measuring 4.5 x 3 x 3.5 cm, with a smooth external surface with focal hemorrhagic areas. On section, it had a lobulated appearance, a reddish-brown color, and an area of hemorrhage and focal necrosis of less than 5%. Microscopically, the primary cells were rounded, with vesicular, prominent nuclei and granular eosinophilic cytoplasm. No atypical mitotic figures, extensive necrotic tissue, or vascular or perineural invasion were observed; there was no evidence of malignancy (Figure 6).

FIGURE 6. Findings consistent with benign carotid paraganglioma, with no histological criteria for malignancy.

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During the 6-month follow-up, no recurrences or vascular or neurological sequelae were reported.

DISCUSSION

Carotid glomus tumors are benign, although they have high surgical potential due to their vascularization and close relationship with neurovascular structures. In this case, they were associated with circumferential involvement of the internal and external carotid arteries, hypoglossal nerve, vagus nerve, and accessory nerve (1, 2).

A 2019 meta-analysis (15) indicates that the Shamblin classification guides surgical planning; and type III tumors are associated with higher morbidity and the need for vascular reconstruction. However, good planning could guide the surgeon to choose a different surgical approach (6, 7, 8, 15). In this clinical case, we present a Shamblin type III tumor, where resection without grafting is performed. This is a rare management option, but possible if careful dissection and primary repair of the bifurcation are achieved (7, 13, 14, 15). Graham et al. (14) report some cases where the approach is more conservative, with good results.

Like Cleere et al. (13), they describe cases with Shamblin III where a graftless approach was performed without preoperative embolization.

Some authors recommend preoperative embolization; however, it is not essential in all cases, as demonstrated in the literature and in this case. The main complications described include cranial nerve injury (IX, X, XI, XII), cerebrovascular events, and massive bleeding, especially in Shamblin II and III. In this case, the complication of a hematoma occurred at the time of extubation, which was treated promptly (10, 11, 12).

Postoperative bleeding is a known complication, usually manageable with timely drainage, as occurred in this case. The absence of dysphonia, dysphagia, or neurological deficit is relevant and highlights the appropriate surgical technique (13).

This report contributes and adds to the evidence that, with meticulous technique, complete resection can be achieved in Shamblin III carotid glomus without the need for vascular grafting, minimizing risks (13, 14, 15).

CONCLUSION

Surgical management of Shamblin III carotid paragangliomas can be performed without vascular grafting in selected cases, with careful primary repair and close postoperative monitoring. This approach can prevent further complications and has proven safe and effective in experienced hands.

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